

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELIGIOUS TOURISM AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT BUNDELKHAND REGION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Studies that examined the correlation between religion tourism and economic development of Bundelkhand region in India had not been reported. This is despite the massive influx of foreign religion tourists to India in particular to seek faith adventures and solution for spiritual challenges. The article determines the perception of Indians, with emphasis on inhabitant of Bundelkhand about the concept of religion tourism and the extent it economically impacted their regions and people of community. It also examines the relationship between religion tourism and dimensions of economic development in Bunelkhand region of India. As far as tourism particularly religious tourism of Bundelkhand region is concerned, the places like Khajuraho, Orchha, Chitrakoot, Jhansi, Gwalior, are the main tourist attractions of the region where foreign tourists as well as indigenous tourists regularly visit for religious and non-religious reasons. Besides these places, there are many sites throughout this region which have remained unexplored. Baruasagar, Shivpuri, Datia, Sonagir, Devgarh, Mahoba, Kalinjar, Panna, Samthar, Morena, Jabalpur, Sagar & Chanderi are such unexplored places which will be become treasure provided they are accorded more coverage. Their share in local economy will increase as a result of tourism marketing and packages. The region is very rustic and rudimentary and this can also be made as an attraction for the foreign tourists who wish to explore the original unpolluted areas of India. The contribution of these destinations in local tourism economy and domestic tourist arrivals is important. Bundelkhand region has lot of cultural and natural tourism resources. However, we fail to get optimum output due to lake of proper advertising management and marketing. The study reveals that the study area of Bundelkhand possesses excellent potential for tourism, most of which even today is virgin and unexplored. The major attractions being in terms of pleasure tourism & religious tourism. The area is filled with historical heritage and attracts tourists who are interested in history, monuments and nature.

Keywords: Religious Tourism, Economic Dimensions, Faith- based Destination, and Bundelkhand Residents.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism industry is one of the prospective economic sectors to develop India at a larger rate and make sure of the consequential growth of the infrastructure at the destinations. It has the potential to capture and capitalize on the country's success in the services sector and contribute sustainable models of development. In India, it is forecasted that per million rupees of investment on tourism and travel sector can generate 78 jobs compared to 45 jobs in the manufacturing sector for same investment. Apart from

providing employment to a broad spectrum of job finders from the unskilled to the specialized skilled, a larger proportion of tourism advantages (jobs, petty trade opportunities) accrue to women.

According to the Tourism Satellite Account for the year 2002-03 arranged by Ministry of Tourism, the direct and indirect contribution of tourism to the GDP and the aggregate employment in the nation from the 2007-08 is measured to be 5.92 % and 9.24 % respectively. Nation's economy has been contributed by three-fourths by the domestic tourism.

Tourism has the prosperous potential to motivate other economic continuums through its forward and backward connections with a host of sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, hospitality, education, transport, banking, health, etc. investment on tourism persuades a chain of transactions requiring supply of goods and services from these associated sectors. The consumption demand, emanating from tourist expenditure also generates larger employment and creates an amplified effect on the economy. As a result, additional incomes, benefits and employment opportunities are created through such connections. Therefore, the expansion of the tourism sector can lead to large scale employment generation and poverty mitigations. The economic benefits that pour into the economy through development of tourism in the form of strengthened national and state revenues, employment, business receipts, wages and salary income, buoyancy in local, state and central tax receipts can contribute towards overall socio-economic growth and accelerated development of the economy. India requires tap the full potential of a sound tourism sector.

Though tourism industry is overwhelmingly of private sector service contributors, the public sector has an important role to play in the provision of infrastructure, either directly or through Public Private Partnership (PPP). It is a multi-sectoral action characterized by multiple services contributed by a range of suppliers. It is completely similar to manufacturing industry, where in which the supply chain is as significant as an end-product. The linked sectors include airlines, hotels, basic infrastructure surface transport and facilitation systems, etc. Therefore, the development of tourism cannot be gained unless the issues associated to all the sectors are addressed simultaneously. Continuing global prosperity, growing identification of tourism's contribution to economic growth and employment, focused marketing and promotion efforts, liberalization of air transport, availability of better infrastructure, growing intraregional cooperation, and more successful Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) are seen as the vital drivers for tourism in upcoming decade.

The development of inbound tourism in India has been brighter than the world. India registered a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.1% throughout 2001 to 2010 as against 3.6% for the world during the same period. United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) has predicted that the travel & tourism industry in India will rise by 8% per annum, in original terms, between 2008 and 2016. Foreign exchange yielding from tourism could show 14% of annual growth during the same period. Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) to India has seen somewhat of a theatrical turnaround from 2002, when a temporary down trend was reversed forcefully. This aggressive trend was the result of various factors such as Government of India's "Incredible India" campaign, the tourism industry's constant seeking for new destinations, high visibility afforded to India by its economic success, and to some extent development in infrastructure in specific areas (such as better air connectivity of smaller and remote destinations). The total number of foreign tourist arrivals in India in 2010 was 5.58 million, registering an

annual growth rate of 8.1% over the year 2009. The foreign exchange incomes from tourism during 2010 were US\$ 14.19 billion with a growth 24.6% over the year 2009. Despite this burgeoning Asian market share, India's total share in world tourist arrivals remains a modest 0.6%. Whether measured by the yardstick of its amplified tourism resources, or its emerging economic significance, India's low share of tourism arrivals is certainly below potential.

Domestic tourism plays a vital role in overall tourism development in the country. The figure of domestic tourist visits (DTV's) grown from 462 million in 2006 to 740 million in 2010. In 2009 when the country witnessed a negative rise of 2.2 % in FTAs, domestic tourist visits registered a growth of 18.8 %. This uptrend of DTV's sustained several tourism infrastructures during negative period for the tourism sector.

Since time immemorial, the urge to travel, explore new places and a fascination for a change from the routine has led to the evolution of tourism. Trade and commerce, quest for knowledge and the exploration of new sites contribute to the development of tourism. There are several motivating factors which make an average person seek tourism. The significance of tourism contributes to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of a country's economy and its growth, generating employment, cross cultural bonding among the global population and declining of borders. Indian tourism has made a significant turnaround from 2017. Places of historical significance and many heritage sites have made India a great prospect for tourism. The Indian Government's campaign '*Incredible India*' has contributed to a great extent to India's prospects in tourism industry.

As far as tourism particularly religious tourism of Bundelkhand region is concerned, the places like Khajuraho, Orchha, Chitrakoot, Jhansi, Gwalior, are the main tourist attractions of the region where foreign tourists as well as indigenous tourists regularly visit for religious and non-religious reasons. Besides these places, there are many sites throughout this region which have remained unexplored. Baruasagar, Shivpuri, Datia, Sonagir, Devgarh, Mahoba, Kalinjar, Panna, Samthar, Morena, Jabalpur, Sagar & Chanderi are such unexplored places which will be become treasure provided they are accorded more coverage. Their share in local economy will increase as a result of tourism marketing and packages. The region is very rustic and rudimentary and this can also be made as an attraction for the foreign tourists who wish to explore the original unpolluted areas of India. The contribution of these destinations in local tourism economy and domestic tourist arrivals is important. Bundelkhand region has lot of cultural and natural tourism resources. However, we fail to get optimum output due to lake of proper advertising management and marketing.

The study reveals that the study area of Bundelkhand possesses excellent potential for tourism, most of which even today is virgin and unexplored. The major attractions being in terms of pleasure tourism & religious tourism. The area is filled with historical heritage and attracts tourists who are interested in history, monuments and nature.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A detailed Literature has been reviewed to make the study relevant. Few among them are:

TABLE 2.1 KEY FINDINGS FROM REVIEW OF LITERATURE

S.No.	Author(Year)	Objectives	Findings
1	Himadri Phukan, Rahman Z. & Devdutt P.(2012)	The aim of the study was emergence of spiritual tourism in India and also analyzed about emergence of spiritual tourism.	The study discovered a model depicting a general classification of tourism literature in the context of increasing research interests in the spiritual tourism has been presented in the form of a model. Finally, the study found that there has been a phenomenal increase in spiritual travelers in the recent years owing to generic changes in the people's attitude towards spirituality. The study identified that ripple effect of this change has also been observed in the academic research. Literatures in the field of spiritual tourism, along with other sector-based tourisms (adventure tourism, eco tourism, medical tourism, wedding tourism etc.), have been on rise significantly.
2	Monika Pandey and Arunesh Parashar (2012)	The purpose of the study was describes the challenges faced by Kerala tourism industry.	This study investigated the positive influence of spiritual tourism on social and spiritual values. Furthermore, it also identified that large number of people are making to religious or holy places as a travel motivator. The paper also conveyed that this practice is widely spread in various parts of the world and it can be observed in Jainism, Christianity and Islamic, Buddhism where in which spirituality has a strong impact on human society by religious movements and institutions. Finally, the authors concluded that there is a significant improvement in the spiritual qualities such as increase in tolerance levels participant or tourists, changes in the lifestyles of the tourist and etc.
3	Pujari Krishnaiah (2012)	The focus of the study was the problems and prospects of tourism in Andhra Pradesh and case analysis of Chittoor district.	The study discovered clearly the gap between demand and supply in terms of availability, quality and variety of accommodation, food and transport related facilities and many other allied services. The study revealed that the supply in terms of the various tourist facilities is not only insufficient but also ineffective. However, the researcher found the Problems and prospects of the twelve dominant attraction centres in particular and of the remaining subsidiary attraction centres in specific and future subsidiary attraction centres in general.
4	Vargheese Antony Jesurajan S. and Varghees Prabhu S. (2012)	The aim of the study was highlight the dimensions of spiritual tourism in Tuiticorin District of Tamil Nadu in India.	The study reveals that evaluate the satisfaction level of tourist and determinants of spiritual tourism and problems faced by tourist in Tuiticorin district. The article found that the problems faced by the tourists include: pollution and lack of cleanliness, beggars' nuisance, lack of sanitary facility and exploitation by taxi and vehicle operators. This study will be relevant and significant to the present Indian scenario.
5	Vijayanand S. (2012)	The purpose of the study was highlight on the origin and evolution of pilgrimage tourism management.	The study conclude that pilgrimage tourism is a manifestation of the increasing acceptance of individuated formations of personal identity, evolution of pilgrimage tourism and the roles of pilgrimage tourism a way to explore concepts of truth, belief, and morality that are typically either ignored or not agreed. The study has revealed the evolution of pilgrimage tourism and the roles of pilgrimage tourism and the economy of pilgrimage tourism in south India. The data presented in this paper indicate the potential for pilgrimage tourism development. The analysis shows that it should be possible to spread the development of pilgrimage tourism to more parts of the region. Particularly taking into account the potential for combining pilgrimage tourism with cultural and nature based tourism and the potential for developing new age or pilgrimage tourism; it should be possible to use the

			major anchor sites identified to stimulate regional development. The study recommended that the Pilgrimage sites can be developed as a heavenly destination for pilgrimage tourism. The overall aim will obviously be to enhance the advantages of religious tourism and its people in terms of foreign exchange, employment generation, income creation, and government revenue in Tamil Nadu
6	Vijayanand S. (2012)	The aim of the study was the pilgrimage tourism management issues and challenges with reference to Tamil Nadu.	The study investigates that, the pilgrimage tourism and its problems and challenges and its cultural significance and socio economic development through pilgrimage tourism and also it analyzed the basic infrastructure issues in pilgrimage sites. The study identified various problems that confront the sustained development of pilgrimage tourism. The data presented in this paper indicate the potential for pilgrimage tourism development. The author determined that, although development has been limited to few major sites, the analysis shows that it should be possible to spread the development of pilgrimage tourism to more parts of the region. The researcher recommended that there is a huge potential for combining pilgrimage tourism with cultural and nature based tourism and the potential for developing new age or pilgrimage tourism. The study found that it is possible to use the major anchor sites identified to stimulated regional development.

3. OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of the current research study is to identify and analyze the *hidden economic development and potential of Bundelkhand region in India in respect of Religious tourism*. Paper also emphasizes to study the secondary objectives as stated below:

- To study the status of Bundelkhand Region for Religious tourism development.
- To study the economic development of region with respect to religious tourism.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A *research problem* in general, refers to some deficiency which a researcher experiences in the context of either a theoretical or practical situation and wants to obtain a solution for the same.

Research Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as the science of studying how the research is done scientifically. The aim of the proposed research is to explore and describe the facts and developments related to the topic of the study.

- **Data Collection-** The present study is based on primary and secondary data collection.
 - (a) **Primary Data Collection** - The primary data are those which are collected for first time hence which are fresh and thus, happen to be original in nature. The unstructured interviews of religious tourist places of Bundelkhand entrepreneur were conducted through which the responses were taken and presented in Case Study.
 - (b) **Secondary Data Collection** - Secondary data are information which has previously been collected by some organization to satisfy its own need but it is being used for the current

research under references for an entirely different reason such as literature, Annual reports, Sales reports, Published sources like books and journals, Research papers, masters and PhD Thesis, Newsletters, Media and authentic Websites.

5. FINDINGS OF STUDY

All religions lead to God. Most of us are believers in God and we express our devotion to him through various rituals and religious practices. According to Hindu religion nobody created nor can anybody destroy God. There is much similarity between this belief and the law of conservation of energy given by the great scientist Einstein, according to which energy can neither be created nor destroyed but can only change its form and matter being also a form of energy.

God's existence cannot be attributed to man, but religion is man's medium to communicate with God, has evolved through a complex of psychologies, geography, historical events and social processes, sometimes serving to the well being of man and sometimes causing tension and strife.

Religion is functional; it expresses and serves many individual, social and cultural needs. The various theories on religion propounded by eminent social scientists shed some light on the need for religion and various religious practices that have evolved around the globe.

Table 2.2 Theories on Religion

Theories on Religion	
Social Scientist	Theory
Tylor & Frazor	Religion exists in order to help people make sense of events which would otherwise be incomprehensible by relying on unseen, hidden forces.
Sigmund Freud	Religion is a mass neurosis and exists as a response to deep emotional conflicts and weaknesses.
Emile Dukheim	Religion is a means of social organization. It is a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is to say, things set apart and forbidden. His focus was on the importance of the concept of the "sacred" and its relevance to the welfare of the community.
Karl Marx	Religion is an illusion whose chief purpose is to provide reasons and an excuse to keep society functioning as it is. Religion is opium of the masses.
Mircea Eliade	Religion is a focus on the sacred. Eliade's understanding rests on two concepts: the sacred and the profane. He focuses on timeless forms of ideas which keep recurring in religions all over the world; he ignores their specific historic contexts.
Stewart Elliot Guthrie	Religion is anthropomorphization gone awry. According to him religion is attribution of human characteristics to non human things or events
EE Evans-Pritchard	Religion has deep emotional roots
Clifford Geertz	Religion as culture and meaning. He treats religion as a vital component of cultural meanings. He argues that religion carries symbols which establish powerful moods or feelings

Source: Monisha Chattopadhyaya (2006), 'Religious Tourism: An Introduction', 'Religion and Tourism – Perspectives', the ICFAI University Press, Hyderabad, pp. 5.-9"

Based on these theories one may say that religion exists as an explanation for what we don't understand, as a psychological reaction to our lives and surroundings, as an expression of social needs, as a tool of the status quo to keep some people in power and others out, as a focus upon supernatural and

sacred aspects of our lives, and as an evolutionary strategy for survival. Religion is a complex human institution. Religion has complex origins and motivations’.

CHARACTERISTICS OF RELIGIOUS TOURISM

Defining religious tourism seems often a tough task. The tourism has got numerous literatures in which different authors had been categorized differently, where religious tourism, spiritual tourism, pilgrimage tourism, cultural tourism and cultural heritage tourism are often referred as synonyms. Because, in most cases cultural tourists prefer to visit pilgrimages as part of their travel, thus they often referred named as religious tourists. Religious tourism is the area where very less studies had been undertaken and interestingly it is also a very old form of tourism.

1. To perform pilgrimage as an act of worship
2. To express gratitude, confess sin and to perform a vow
3. To achieve social and spiritual salvation
4. To commemorate and celebrate certain religious events
5. To be in communication with co-religionists

Religious tourism can be categorized into three categories. They are.

1. Pilgrimages
2. Volunteer or Missionary travel
3. Religious events and Fellowship travel

Some places of tourist interest in this region are-Jhansi, Orchha, Barusagar, Shivpuri, Datia, Sonagir, Deogarh, Mahoba, Chitrakoot, Kalinjar, Khajuraho, Panna, Samthar, Gwalior, Morena, Jabalpur, Sagar, Chanderi etc.

Jhansi, the gateway of Bundelkhand, was a stronghold of the Chandelas kings but lost its importance after the eclipse of the dynasty in the 11th Century. It rose to prominence again in the 17th century under Raja Bir singh Ju Deo, who was a close associate of the Mughal Emperor Jahangir. However, its greatest claim to fame is its queen Laxmi Bai, who led forces against the British in 1857, sacrificing her life to the cause of Indian Independence. A new dimension has been added to this historic city with the introduction of the Jhansi Festival, held every year in February-March. It offers a fine opportunity to enjoy the arts, crafts and culture of the region.

Table 2.3: Tourists arrivals at Bundelkhand

Year	Domestic	International	Total
2010	492611	9941	502552
2011	360630	3805	364435
2012	382800	3854	386654
2013	629037	5543	634580
2014	972798	7955	980753
2015	978942	8122	987064
2016	976471	8422	984893

Maurya M.L. & Garg S.K. / Exploring the Relationship Between Religious Tourism and Economic Development Bundelkhand Region in India

Psychometric test of the independent variable (i.e. Religion Tourism), and four dimensions of economy was tested, and the results of the reliability coefficient of individual items met the threshold Cronbach's alpha (α) value $> .7$ (Pallant, 2010). Hence; the Cronbach's alpha (α) value of religion tourism (RT) is 0.673; employment generation (EG) is 0.805; revenue / income generation (RIG), 0.825; investment promotion (INP), 0.847, and infrastructural development (INF), 0.812. This suggests that all the items measures underlying dimensions consistently (Coakes et al., 2009). The composite reliability score for aggregate dimensions of economic development (SPT) is 0.810. This implies that items for the measures of economy in respect of Bundelkhand Region are moderately and internally consistent (Barrett, 2007).

The results of analysis of extent religion tourism generates employment opportunities for inhabitants of Bundelkhand region shows that majority of the respondents were of the view that religion tourism encourages entrepreneurs drive, provides both direct and indirect employment opportunities, and creates job satisfaction for the resident of Bundelkhand region.

This result is in consonance with the previous studies in domain of tourism as reported in Yan & Wall (2002) and Archer & Fletcher (1996). These studies agree that tourism encourages entrepreneurial drives in local residents, and provide jobs opportunities. The finale that could be drawn from this study is that religion tourism support employment generation.

The implication of this for Indian Government is to encourage the growth of this industry through feasible policy thrusts. The results of the extent that religion tourism generate revenue to the local residence shows that tourist expenditure through religion tourism enhances output multiplier of the locals, improve the quality of health and welfare of residents, boosts local business turnover, and income multiplier of the locals.

These results are in consonance with previous literature in domain of tourism as reported in Vanhove (2005); and Dwyer et al. (2004). The results that could be reached based on this study is that the income generation capacity of local residence in Bundelkhand region is enhanced through religion tourism events hosted in the area. The implication of this is urgent government involvement through security support and infrastructure development.

Furthermore, the outcome of analysis on the extent of investment promotion capacity of religion tourism in Bundelkhand region shows that religion tourism activities brand image of Bundelkhand region positively, enhances investment opportunities domicile in Bundelkhand region, and supported the growth of small scale business enterprise in the area. The implication of this result is aggressive marketing of religion event in India, including provision of amenities that support ease of doing business in the host communities.

In addition the result of the extent religion tourism supports infrastructure development in Bundelkhand region shows that religion tourism encourages environmental sustainability, enhance local transportation infrastructure, and facilitates social and cultural infrastructure development of the host community. It also enhances and sustains good living condition of the local residence..

6. CONCLUSION

As far as tourism particularly religious tourism of Bundelkhand region is concerned, the places like Khajuraho, Orchha, Chitrakoot, Jhansi, Gwalior, are the main tourist attractions of the region where foreign tourists as well as indigenous tourists regularly visit for religious and non-religious reasons. Besides these places, there are many sites throughout this region which have remained unexplored. Baruasagar, Shivpuri, Datia, Sonagir, Devgarh, Mahoba, Kalinjar, Panna, Samthar, Morena, Jabalpur, Sagar & Chanderi are such unexplored places which will become treasure provided they are accorded more coverage. Their share in local economy will increase as a result of tourism marketing and packages. The region is very rustic and rudimentary and this can also be made as an attraction for the foreign tourists who wish to explore the original unpolluted areas of India. The contribution of these destinations in local tourism economy and domestic tourist arrivals is important. Bundelkhand region has lot of cultural and natural tourism resources. However, we fail to get optimum output due to lack of proper advertising management and marketing. The study reveals that the study area of Bundelkhand possesses excellent potential for tourism, most of which even today is virgin and unexplored. The major attractions being in terms of pleasure tourism & religious tourism. The area is filled with historical heritage and attracts tourists who are interested in history, monuments and nature.

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